

Stochastic Cruise Speed Control for Time-Based Metering Under Uncertainty

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Abstract—The increasing demand for aviation necessitates safe and efficient air traffic management strategies, such as time-based metering operations, which manage controlled times of arrival (CTAs) at designated fixes. These operations rely on precise speed control to ensure aircraft meet their CTAs. However, current deterministic approaches to speed control fail to account for inherent uncertainties in aircraft operations, particularly those arising from weather prediction inaccuracies. This study proposes a Markov decision process framework for time-based metering during cruise, addressing the critical trade-off between delay uncertainty and the operational costs. The framework incorporates the number of speed changes into the state space, recognizing that frequent speed adjustments are operationally undesirable and significantly increase the workload of pilots and air traffic controllers. To mitigate this, the proposed approach caps the number of speed changes and determines the optimal speed and timing of speed changes under uncertainty, reducing delays and fuel consumption while enhancing operational feasibility. Numerical simulations validate the proposed method, demonstrating its ability to achieve optimal performance with a limited number of speed changes while ensuring adherence to CTAs. This research highlights the potential of stochastic cruise speed control to improve air traffic management by integrating realistic uncertainty models and operational constraints.

Keywords—flight time uncertainty; Markov decision process; speed control; time-based metering operations; trajectory-based operations

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past few decades, the demand for aviation has increased significantly. Despite the global COVID-19 pandemic, long-term growth in the aviation sector is expected to resume gradually [1]. The basic concept aimed at improving the safety and efficiency of air transportation is the four-dimensional (4D) trajectory-based operations (TBO), which accurately describe an aircraft's path in three-dimensional space and time. TBO aims to manage the 4D trajectory of an aircraft strategically, and its implementation requires

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time-based metering operations. During time-based metering operations, each aircraft receives instructions from air traffic control (ATC) to pass a specific waypoint (metering fix) on its route at a specified controlled time of arrival (CTA) to facilitate merging, spacing, and sequencing. ATC strategically deconflicts at the metering fix by assigning a CTA to each aircraft to ensure proper spacing between aircraft; aircraft speed must be controlled to meet the CTA, and time-based metering operations depend on proper speed control to absorb delays. Speed control strategies have been shown to effectively mitigate airborne holding and radar vectoring and improve flight efficiency [2], [3].

New avionics and operational concepts are being researched and developed to support metering operations: time and energy management operations [4], [5] and flight-deck interval management [6], [7]. These approaches propose speed control methods to comply with CTA and achieve accurate spacing between aircraft. Another study [8] has also proposed a speed control method that applies model predictive control. However, these studies use deterministic approaches that do not consider the uncertainties inherent in aircraft operations. As Cook et al. [9] points out, aircraft trajectories are affected by various uncertainties, including weather prediction inaccuracies. While the uncertainties introduce variability in the aircraft trajectory, deterministic approaches cannot assess the effects and propagation of these uncertainties. It is critical to consider the effects of uncertainty on aircraft trajectories because inadequate consideration can lead to significant discrepancies between the planned and actual trajectories.

The research by Tan et al. [10] analyzed the impact of wind forecast uncertainty on TBO and proposed an optimization framework for locating metering points and managing operational parameters to improve efficiency, throughput, and fuel consumption in air traffic management (ATM). Stochastic optimization, a complex and challenging area of study in the field of ATM, has been particularly focused on optimization problems involving weather uncertainties. Jung and Clarke's work [11] proposed a stochastic algorithm that optimally adjusts cruise airspeeds in real-time to minimize fuel consumption while meeting required times of arrival under wind uncertainty, demonstrating its effectiveness in both single and multiple aircraft scenarios.

A Markov decision process (MDP) [12], a classical framework for modeling decisions with uncertainty, has also been instrumental in studying a wide range of stochastic optimization problems in ATM. Nilim et al. [13] proposed a dynamic routing strategy under uncertain weather conditions, Kochenderfer et al. [14] designed an uncertainty-aware collision avoidance system, and Cox and Kochenderfer [15] applied an MDP for planning ground delay programs. Gaydos et al. [16] formulated time-based metering operations as an MDP, and demonstrated the feasibility of designing an optimal control law that accounts for trajectory uncertainty. However, the following issues remain because it was a simplified model that only considered residual delay as the state space. The calculation of fuel cost and flight time needs to be more accurate because the speed change is assumed to be instantaneous, ignoring acceleration. In addition, the number of speed changes increases frequently because speed changes are allowed at each discretized time step. In the flight demonstration of flight-deck interval management [6], [7] described earlier, a high frequency of speed changes was observed, and it was pointed out that a high frequency of speed changes is undesirable for operations and increases the pilots' workload too much. Therefore, it is desirable to perform speed control with as few speed changes as possible, considering the implementation of actual operations.

In this study, we further extend the work of Gaydos et al. [16] by introducing speed and the number of speed changes into the state space. Since an MDP discretizes the state space, it can easily handle discrete state variables such as the number of speed changes. When changing speeds under trajectory uncertainty, it is important to allow some opportunity for the variation in delay from the CTA to be offset by the uncertainty. Therefore, this study proposes a speed control method that can optimize, in a stochastic context, the best times to change speed within a limited number of speed changes. Our proposed method considers the trade-off between the uncertainty and the cost associated with speed changes to satisfy the CTA.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II introduces the aircraft dynamics and flight time uncertainty model. Section III describes the MDP formulation for time-based metering operations. Section IV demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed speed control method through illustrative numerical simulations. Finally, Section V presents the conclusions.

II. FLIGHT TIME UNCERTAINTY

This section describes typical aircraft dynamics and introduces the flight time uncertainty model.

A. Aircraft Dynamics

This study addresses time-based metering operations during the cruise phase. A typical commercial flight defines the lateral path by a sequence of predetermined fixes along a

planned route. Therefore, our focus is solely on the aircraft dynamics described by the following equations:

$$\frac{ds}{dt} = v_{GS} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dv_{TAS}}{dt} = \frac{Th - D}{m} - \left(\frac{dw_n}{dt} \cos \chi + \frac{dw_e}{dt} \sin \chi \right) \cos \gamma_a \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = -FF \quad (3)$$

where t is the time; s is the along-track distance; v_{GS} is the ground speed; v_{TAS} is the true airspeed; Th and D are the thrust and drag forces, respectively; m is the aircraft weight; w_n and w_e denote the northward and eastward components of the wind vector, respectively; dw_n/dt and dw_e/dt are the windshear terms; χ represents the heading angle; γ_a is the air flight path angle; and FF is the fuel flow. γ_a during the cruise phase is sufficiently small to approximate $\cos \gamma_a \simeq 1$. D and FF are obtained from the base of aircraft data (BADA) Family 4 [17], an aircraft performance model developed by EUROCONTROL. v_{GS} in (1) and χ in (2) are derived from the velocity triangle by approximating $\cos \gamma_a \simeq 1$, as follows:

$$v_{GS} = \sqrt{v_{TAS}^2 - w_c^2} + w_a \quad (4)$$

$$\chi = \psi + \arcsin \frac{w_c}{v_{TAS}}$$

where w_c and w_a represent the wind vector's cross- and along-track components, respectively, and ψ denotes the true track angle. Because the lateral path is predetermined as a planned route, ψ dependent on the lateral path can be expressed as a predefined function of s . In addition, w_c and w_a are calculated from w_n , w_e , and ψ using the following equations:

$$w_c = w_n \sin \psi - w_e \cos \psi$$

$$w_a = w_n \cos \psi + w_e \sin \psi$$

Weather prediction data provided by numerical weather prediction agencies typically consists of grid point values for w_n and w_e , which can be determined by prescribed functions of s . Therefore, w_c and w_a are given by the prescribed functions of s .

It also introduces the Mach number M . Using M , v_{TAS} is expressed by the following equation:

$$v_{TAS} = M\sqrt{\kappa RT}$$

where κ is the adiabatic index of air and is set to 1.4; R is the real gas constant for air and is set to $287.05287 \text{ m}^2/(\text{K} \cdot \text{s}^2)$; and T is the air temperature, obtained from weather prediction data as well as w_n and w_e . Accordingly, v_{GS} in (4) is given by:

$$v_{GS} = \sqrt{M^2 \kappa RT - w_c^2} + w_a \quad (5)$$

Next, we describe the trajectory calculation. In (1), s consistently increases relative to t because v_{GS} remains positive for the fixed-wing aircraft considered in this study.

Consequently, we use s instead of t as the independent variable. Eqs. (1)–(3) can be reformulated as follows:

$$\frac{dt}{ds} = \frac{1}{v_{GS}} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dv_{TAS}}{ds} &= \frac{dv_{TAS}}{dt} \frac{dt}{ds} \\ &= \frac{Th - D}{mv_{GS}} - \left(\frac{dw_n}{ds} \cos \chi + \frac{dw_e}{ds} \sin \chi \right) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dm}{ds} &= \frac{dm}{dt} \frac{dt}{ds} \\ &= -\frac{FF}{v_{GS}} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

We can calculate the trajectory by numerically integrating Eqs. (6)–(8).

B. Uncertainty Model

An uncertainty model plays a vital role in formulating the MDP. To address uncertainty in numerical weather prediction, ensemble weather forecasting [18] has been developed. This approach generates multiple forecasts by perturbing initial conditions or atmospheric parameters. In ATM research, ensemble forecasts have recently been applied to trajectory prediction [19] and flight planning [20]. However, this study utilizes a previously developed flight time uncertainty model [21], [22]. Derived from a flight time estimation algorithm, this model estimates the uncertainty of an aircraft's flight time over arbitrary distances under various weather conditions.

In this subsection, we briefly describe the modeling of flight time uncertainty. The flight time uncertainty model is derived from a flight time estimation algorithm. The estimated time of arrival (ETA) to a specific position t_{ETA} is determined by the flight distance to that position d and the ground speed v_{GS} as follows:

$$t_{ETA} = \frac{d}{v_{GS}} \quad (9)$$

Using (5), (9) can be rewritten as:

$$t_{ETA} = \frac{d}{\sqrt{M^2 \kappa RT - w_c^2} + w_a} \quad (10)$$

In (10), d , κ , and R are deterministic fixed values, while w_a , w_c , T , and M contain uncertainties and are sources of the uncertainty in t_{ETA} . Assuming that the error in t_{ETA} follows a Gaussian distribution, the variance of the error σ_{ETA}^2 is obtained as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{ETA}^2 &= \left(\frac{\partial t_{ETA}}{\partial w_a} \right)^2 \sigma_{w_a}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial t_{ETA}}{\partial w_c} \right)^2 \sigma_{w_c}^2 \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{\partial t_{ETA}}{\partial T} \right)^2 \sigma_T^2 + \left(\frac{\partial t_{ETA}}{\partial M} \right)^2 \sigma_M^2 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $\sigma_{w_a}^2$, $\sigma_{w_c}^2$, σ_T^2 , and σ_M^2 represent the variances of w_a , w_c , T , and M , respectively, and are assumed to be independent of each other. While these variables may exhibit some correlation in practice (particularly w_a and w_c), the independence assumption is made for simplicity. Equation (11) suggests that σ_{ETA}^2 can be derived solely from flight

conditions such as distance and speed, as well as weather conditions such as wind and temperature.

Equation (11) is particularly derived from actual past flight data and weather prediction data. By introducing new coefficients α_w , α_T , and α_M , (11) can be reformulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{ETA}^2 &= \alpha_w \left(\frac{d}{v_{GS}^2} \right)^2 \left(1 + \left(\frac{w_c}{\sqrt{M^2 \kappa RT - w_c^2}} \right)^2 \right) \sigma_{w,\text{pred}}^2 \\ &\quad + \alpha_T \left(\frac{d}{v_{GS}^2} \right)^2 \left(\frac{M^2 \kappa R}{2\sqrt{M^2 \kappa RT - w_c^2}} \right)^2 \sigma_{T,\text{pred}}^2 \\ &\quad + \alpha_M \left(\frac{d}{v_{GS}^2} \right)^2 \left(\frac{M \kappa RT}{\sqrt{M^2 \kappa RT - w_c^2}} \right)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $\sigma_{w,\text{pred}}^2$ and $\sigma_{T,\text{pred}}^2$ represent the variances of wind and temperature, respectively, obtained from weather prediction data. These variances are calculated using forecasts corresponding to the date and time of the flight for which the flight time uncertainty is being estimated. Further details are provided in Section III-D. In (11), $\sigma_{w_a}^2$ and $\sigma_{w_c}^2$ are assumed to be equal to σ_w^2 . Additionally, the aircraft is usually controlled to maintain a constant Mach number during cruise. Thus, σ_M^2 in (11) can be interpreted as a control error in the aircraft's attempt to maintain a constant Mach number. It is treated as a constant and is included in α_M . Next, the coefficients α_w , α_T , and α_M are determined. The statistics of σ_{ETA}^2 and the terms in (12), excluding these coefficients, are analyzed using historical flight and weather prediction data. In this study, these coefficients are estimated to ensure that the model in (12) effectively captures the dispersion of errors arising from ETA predictions made by (9), using actual data. This study determines that $\alpha_w = 0.2143$, $\alpha_T = 4.2647$, and $\alpha_M = 6.9748 \times 10^{-5}$ using data observed in January, April, July, and October of 2017 and 2018. Further details on modeling flight time uncertainty can be found in [21], [22].

III. MARKOV DECISION PROCESS FORMULATION FOR TIME-BASED METERING OPERATIONS

A time-based metering operation, aimed at controlling aircraft speed to meet a CTA at a metering fix t_{CTA} , is formulated as an MDP. An MDP is defined by a state space, an action space, a reward model (costs associated with specific pairs of states and actions), and a transition model (probability of transitioning to a different state by taking a given action). The objective of an MDP is to determine an optimal policy (mapping from the state space to the action space). The subsequent subsections provide a detailed description of the MDP formulation for the metering operation.

A. State Space

The set of possible states in the MDP is denoted as \mathcal{X} . A state $x \in \mathcal{X}$ consists of four elements: distance s , Mach number M , residual delay $t_{ETA} - t_{CTA}$ at a metering fix, and the remaining number of possible speed changes (or ATC instructions), denoted as n , where t_{CTA} is the CTA at the metering fix, and the residual delay is the difference

between the ETA and the CTA. The state space is discretized into a four-dimensional grid. Specifically, s is discretized equidistantly at intervals of s_f/N , where s_f represents the total flight distance over which the metering operation is implemented, and N is the length of the finite time horizon. M is discretized from M_{\min} to M_{\max} at intervals of 0.01, where M_{\min} and M_{\max} are determined for each aircraft type from the BADA Family 4 aircraft performance model [17]. $t_{\text{ETA}} - t_{\text{CTA}}$ is discretized from -120 to 120 s at intervals of 1 s. n ranges from 0 to N . The state at time step τ is denoted as x_τ , where $\tau = 0, 1, \dots, N$.

B. Action Space

The action space is denoted as \mathcal{A} . An action $a \in \mathcal{A}$ represents the speed (Mach number) advisory provided to the pilot at each time step, ranging from M_{\min} to M_{\max} in intervals of 0.01. The action at time step τ is denoted as a_τ .

C. Reward Model

The immediate reward for taking action a_τ from state x_τ is denoted as $R(x_\tau, a_\tau)$. In this study, the immediate reward is defined as the fuel cost in dollars. Let $m_f(x_\tau, a_\tau)$ represent the fuel consumption when taking action a_τ from state x_τ . m_f is calculated through numerical integration of Eqs. (6)–(8). This study accounts for acceleration and deceleration. When $M_\tau = a_\tau$, the thrust Th is determined from (7) under the condition of a constant Mach number of M_τ . If $M_\tau < a_\tau$ (indicating acceleration), Th is set to the maximum thrust Th_{\max} ; conversely, if $M_\tau > a_\tau$ (indicating deceleration), Th is set to the idle thrust Th_{idle} . Both Th_{\max} and Th_{idle} are obtained from the BADA model. While Th_{\max} and Th_{idle} may not correspond exactly to operational acceleration and deceleration thrust settings during cruise, they are adopted in this study as simplified representations. Once a_τ is reached, Th is recalculated from (7) under the condition of a constant Mach number of a_τ . However, in this study, the aircraft weight is not included in the state x , and m_f is calculated assuming a constant aircraft weight. The aircraft weight is set to 80% of the nominal weight in the BADA model based on a comparison of the actual weight and the nominal weight in the BADA model from previous research [23]. While fuel consumption and minimum speed vary with aircraft weight, their influence is beyond the scope of this study. We convert m_f to R using a jet fuel price. For this conversion, we utilize the 2018 jet fuel price of \$86.1 per barrel [24]¹. Note that the specific gravity of jet fuel is assumed to be 6.8 lb/U.S. gallon [25]².

In addition, the value function of the terminal state is denoted as $V_f(x_N)$. In this study, $V_f(x_N)$ is defined as a cost in dollars according to the actual delay $t_{\text{ATA}} - t_{\text{CTA}}$ at a metering fix, where t_{ATA} is the actual time of arrival (ATA) at a metering fix. Note that the ETA in the terminal state ($t_{\text{ETA},N}$) is consistent with t_{ATA} . $V_f(x_N)$ depends on whether $t_{\text{ATA}} - t_{\text{CTA}}$ is positive or negative. When $t_{\text{ATA}} - t_{\text{CTA}} \leq 0$, the aircraft arrives at the metering fix early

Figure 1: Terminal cost relative to delay.

and needs to fly the additional time $|t_{\text{ATA}} - t_{\text{CTA}}|$ due to the early arrival. Assume the additional time is absorbed through measures such as path stretching, though the details of the measures are not explicitly modeled. Instead, the fuel cost of flying the additional time $|t_{\text{ATA}} - t_{\text{CTA}}|$ at terminal speed M_N is defined as $V_f(x_N)$ for $t_{\text{ATA}} - t_{\text{CTA}} \leq 0$. Conversely, when $t_{\text{ATA}} - t_{\text{CTA}} > 0$, the aircraft is delayed at the metering fix, resulting in a capacity loss. Assuming an arrival separation of two min, there is a capacity loss of one aircraft per two-min delay. The capacity loss cost is calculated using the 2018 net profit per passenger of \$6.2 [24] and the number of passengers for each aircraft type based on the aircraft performance database developed by EUROCONTROL³. This capacity loss cost is $V_f(x_N)$ for $t_{\text{ATA}} - t_{\text{CTA}} > 0$.

Fig. 1 illustrates $V_f(x_N)$ using a wide-body jet aircraft as an example. The fuel cost for $t_{\text{ATA}} - t_{\text{CTA}} \leq 0$ is calculated assuming a terminal speed of $M_N = 0.8$ at a cruise altitude of 39,000 ft. For the capacity loss cost associated with $t_{\text{ATA}} - t_{\text{CTA}} > 0$, it is assumed that there are 269 passengers per aircraft, resulting in a capacity loss cost of $\$6.2 \times 269$ per aircraft for every two-min delay.

D. Transition Model

The probability for transitioning from state x_τ to $x_{\tau+1}$ with action a_τ is denoted as $T(x_\tau, a_\tau, x_{\tau+1})$. The state transition probability is defined for each state element. The current distance $s_\tau (= s_f \tau / N)$ always increments to the next distance $s_{\tau+1} (= s_f (\tau + 1) / N)$. The current Mach number M_τ becomes $M_{\tau+1}$ at the next time step by taking action a_τ . When $M_\tau = a_\tau$, the current remaining number of possible speed changes n_τ remains unchanged at the next time step ($n_{\tau+1} = n_\tau$), while when $M_\tau \neq a_\tau$, n_τ decreases by one ($n_{\tau+1} = n_\tau - 1$). Finally, regarding $t_{\text{ETA}} - t_{\text{CTA}}$, the current $t_{\text{ETA},\tau} - t_{\text{CTA}}$ is affected by the uncertainty in the interval from s_τ to $s_{\tau+1}$, and the transition probability to $t_{\text{ETA},\tau+1} - t_{\text{CTA}}$ at the next time step follows a Gaussian distribution as described in Section II and is represented by

¹1 barrel = 42 U.S. gallons

²1 lb = 0.45359237 kg

³<https://contentzone.eurocontrol.int/aircraftperformance/>

$\mathcal{N}(\bar{t}_{\text{ETA},\tau} - t_{\text{CTA}}, \sigma_{\text{ETA},\tau}^2)$ with mean $\bar{t}_{\text{ETA},\tau} - t_{\text{CTA}}$ and variance $\sigma_{\text{ETA},\tau}^2$ of the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{\text{ETA},\tau}^2 = & \\ & \alpha_w \left(\frac{s_f/N}{v_{\text{GS},\tau}^2} \right)^2 \left(1 + \left(\frac{w_{c,\tau}}{\sqrt{a_\tau^2 \kappa R T_\tau - w_{c,\tau}^2}} \right)^2 \right) \sigma_{w,\text{pred},\tau}^2 \\ & + \alpha_T \left(\frac{s_f/N}{v_{\text{GS},\tau}^2} \right)^2 \left(\frac{a_\tau^2 \kappa R}{2\sqrt{a_\tau^2 \kappa R T_\tau - w_{c,\tau}^2}} \right)^2 \sigma_{T,\text{pred},\tau}^2 \\ & + \alpha_M \left(\frac{s_f/N}{v_{\text{GS},\tau}^2} \right)^2 \left(\frac{a_\tau \kappa R T_\tau}{\sqrt{a_\tau^2 \kappa R T_\tau - w_{c,\tau}^2}} \right)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where $v_{\text{GS},\tau} = \sqrt{a_\tau^2 \kappa R T_\tau - w_{c,\tau}^2} + w_{a,\tau}$. $\bar{t}_{\text{ETA},\tau}$ is the deterministic ETA to the metering fix resulting from action a_τ at the current Mach number M_τ . It is calculated using (9), and when acceleration or deceleration is considered, it is obtained through numerical integration of Eqs. (6)–(8), similarly to m_f in the reward model from the previous subsection. Note that t_{CTA} is a deterministic fixed value. $\sigma_{w,\text{pred},\tau}^2$ and $\sigma_{T,\text{pred},\tau}^2$ are determined by the following equations [21], [22]:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{w,\text{pred},\tau}^2 &= \frac{1}{N-\tau} \sum_{i=\tau}^N \|w_i - w_\tau\|^2 \\ \sigma_{T,\text{pred},\tau}^2 &= \frac{1}{N-\tau} \sum_{i=\tau}^N (T_i - T_\tau)^2 \end{aligned}$$

where w_i is the wind vector and $w_i = (w_{a,i}, w_{c,i})^\top$. Therefore, the transition probability from $t_{\text{ETA},\tau} - t_{\text{CTA}}$ to $t_{\text{ETA},\tau+1} - t_{\text{CTA}}$ with action a_τ follows the Gaussian distribution $\mathcal{N}(\bar{t}_{\text{ETA},\tau} - t_{\text{CTA}}, \sigma_{\text{ETA},\tau}^2)$ and is given by $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_{\text{ETA},\tau}^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(t_{\text{ETA},\tau+1} - \bar{t}_{\text{ETA},\tau})^2}{2\sigma_{\text{ETA},\tau}^2}\right)$.

In addition, a discrete state space \mathcal{X} is considered in this study. Therefore, the transition probability $T(x_\tau, a_\tau, x_{\tau+1})$ is normalized to satisfy $\sum_{x_{\tau+1} \in \mathcal{X}} T(x_\tau, a_\tau, x_{\tau+1}) = 1$.

E. Policy

The policy of an MDP is a function that specifies which action to perform in each state. In our problem, the policy provides the optimal speed instruction at each state. The solution of the MDP is the policy that maximizes (or minimizes in our problem) the expected sum of rewards. Let $V^*(x_\tau)$ denote the optimal state value function when the optimal policy is followed from state x_τ . $V^*(x_\tau)$ is expressed by the following equation:

$$V^*(x_\tau) = \min_{a_\tau \in \mathcal{A}} \left[R(x_\tau, a_\tau) + \sum_{x_{\tau+1} \in \mathcal{X}} T(x_\tau, a_\tau, x_{\tau+1}) V^*(x_{\tau+1}) \right] \quad (14)$$

In addition, the optimal policy $\Pi^*(x_\tau)$ is obtained as follows:

$$\Pi^*(x_\tau) = \arg \min_{a_\tau \in \mathcal{A}} \left[R(x_\tau, a_\tau) + \sum_{x_{\tau+1} \in \mathcal{X}} T(x_\tau, a_\tau, x_{\tau+1}) V^*(x_{\tau+1}) \right] \quad (15)$$

Equation (14) is also known as the Bellman equation [26]. The Bellman equation states that the input when obtaining the policy depends only on the state at that time x_τ . The property of the MDP, where the optimal policy provides the optimal action in the remaining states after that time, regardless of past action choices, is called Bellman's principle of optimality.

A standard method for computing the optimal state value function is value iteration (also known as backward induction) [12], which updates the state value function at every state using the Bellman equation, a key component in this process. The update process is iterated until convergence; however, because the problem in this study is a finite horizon problem, it can be solved in a single iteration. Value iteration is outlined in Algorithm 1. First, we assign $V^*(x_N) = V_f(x_N)$ to all states at the terminal time step $\tau = N$. Then, the state-action value function $Q(x_\tau, a_\tau)$ is calculated for all states and actions at the time step $\tau = N - 1$, where $Q(x_\tau, a_\tau)$ is given by the expected sum of rewards for taking action a_τ from state x_τ :

$$Q(x_\tau, a_\tau) = R(x_\tau, a_\tau) + \sum_{x_{\tau+1} \in \mathcal{X}} T(x_\tau, a_\tau, x_{\tau+1}) V^*(x_{\tau+1}) \quad (16)$$

$Q(x_\tau, a_\tau)$ is computed over the discrete state and action spaces; once $Q(x_\tau, a_\tau)$ at the time step τ is known, the optimal state value function and optimal policy for all the states at the τ time step are determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} V^*(x_\tau) &= \min_{a_\tau \in \mathcal{A}} Q(x_\tau, a_\tau) \\ \Pi^*(x_\tau) &= \arg \min_{a_\tau \in \mathcal{A}} Q(x_\tau, a_\tau) \end{aligned}$$

By working backwards in time steps, the optimal state value function and optimal policy can be determined using the solution for future states. This solution is derived from the Bellman equation, a fundamental principle in value iteration.

IV. NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

A. Problem Description

This study analyzes a route from Fukuoka Airport to Tokyo International Airport, a popular route in Japan [27]. Fig. 2 shows the planned route obtained from the Japan Aeronautical Information Service Center⁴. The initial and terminal positions for metering operations are defined by existing fixes: HALKA (initial fix) and SPENS (metering fix), with the planned route following a great circle between these two fixes. The total flight distance is 201.5 NM⁵ ($= s_f$), and it is assumed that the aircraft cruises this section at a constant cruise altitude. N is set to 20, and the aircraft completes the total flight distance s_f at $\tau = 20$.

⁴<https://aisjapan.mlit.go.jp>

⁵1 NM = 1852 m

Algorithm 1 Value iteration

Input: $R(x_\tau, a_\tau)$, $V_f(x_N)$, and $T(x_\tau, a_\tau, x_{\tau+1})$
Output: $\Pi^*(x_\tau)$

- 1: **for** $x_N \in \mathcal{X}$ **do**
 - 2: $V^*(x_N) \leftarrow V_f(x_N)$
 - 3: **end for**
 - 4: **for** $\tau = N - 1$ **to** 0 **do**
 - 5: **for** $x_\tau \in \mathcal{X}$ **do**
 - 6: **for** $a_\tau \in \mathcal{A}$ **do**
 - 7: $Q(x_\tau, a_\tau) \leftarrow$ Equation (16)
 - 8: **end for**
 - 9: $V^*(x_\tau) \leftarrow \min_{a_\tau \in \mathcal{A}} Q(x_\tau, a_\tau)$
 - 10: $\Pi^*(x_\tau) \leftarrow \arg \min_{a_\tau \in \mathcal{A}} Q(x_\tau, a_\tau)$
 - 11: **end for**
 - 12: **end for** **return** $\Pi^*(x_\tau), \forall x_\tau \in \mathcal{X}$ ($\tau = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1$)
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Figure 2: Planned route with a total flight distance of 201.5 NM.

The Japan Civil Aviation Bureau has published a set of radar track data for all scheduled civil instrument flight rules flights in Japan’s airspace [28]. The track data are derived from surveillance radar and include time histories of longitude, latitude, and altitude, as well as data on assigned pseudo-call signs and aircraft types. The track data are published for one week each month. A total of 28 days of track data from January, April, July, and October of 2018 are used in this study to match the dates on which the flight time uncertainty model was developed. In time-based metering operations, speed control is applied to meet a specified CTA t_{CTA} . However, as indicated by the analysis by [29], the delay achievable through cruise speed control varies depending on flight conditions, such as cruise altitude and wind speed. On short-haul routes, such as the Japanese domestic flights considered in this study, there are flights for which even a one-min delay is challenging to achieve [30]. There are a total of 1,489 flights across 28 days of track data. Of these, this study analyzes 1,205 flights that can be delayed by more than one min through cruise speed control. The initial speed,

Figure 3: Histograms and density heatmap of initial Mach numbers and cruise flight levels.

Figure 4: Histogram of aircraft types.

cruise altitude, and aircraft type are obtained from the radar track data. The speed and altitude at the position closest to the initial fix obtained from the track data are extracted and set as the initial speed and cruise altitude. Note that the ground speed is estimated by using the time history of latitude and longitude in the track data.

Regarding the meteorological data, we use the mesoscale model (MSM) provided by the Japan Meteorological Agency for numerical weather prediction data. The MSM data⁶ contain atmospheric characteristics such as wind and temperature on a three-dimensional (3D) grid and are published every three hours. The 3D grid points are located at every 0.125 degrees in longitude, 0.1 degrees in latitude, and 50–100 hPa pressure altitudes. In this study, the initial values of MSM data are assumed as the true values of the meteorological data, and the 6-hour forecast values of MSM data are used for the forecast values in the MDP. We use the meteorological data corresponding to the date and time of each of the 1,205 flights to be analyzed.

Fig. 3 presents the histograms and density heatmap of

⁶The data were collected and distributed by Research Institute for Sustainable Humanosphere, Kyoto University (<http://database.rish.kyoto-u.ac.jp/index-e.html>).

initial speeds (Mach numbers) and cruise altitudes (flight levels) for the 1,205 flights analyzed in this study. Initial speeds are converted from ground speeds and MSM data into Mach numbers. Relative frequencies are calculated based on the total number of flights. Significant variation is observed in Mach numbers and flight levels, even for flights on the same route. The frequencies of Mach 0.78 at flight levels 370 and 390, and Mach 0.83 at flight levels 370 and 350, are particularly high. Additionally, Fig. 4 shows the histogram of aircraft types for the 1,205 flights, with a total of seven types identified. Four types (B738, B772, A320, and B763) account for more than 90% of the total flights.

In time-based metering operations, aircraft are assumed to fly along a planned route and use only speed control to meet t_{CTA} . Speed control using MDP determines the optimal action (Mach number) at a given state (distance, Mach number, residual delay, and the remaining number of possible speed changes). The baseline for comparison against speed control using MDP is the ground automation tool currently employed by ATC for metering operations [31]. The automation tool utilizes a deterministic speed control strategy that does not account for uncertainty and calculates the speed required for the aircraft to meet the CTA at the metering fix. At each time step, t_{ETA} in (9) is computed without considering uncertainty. The ground speed used to estimate t_{ETA} is assumed to be constant and equal to the ground speed at the time step when the estimate is performed. Weather predictions along the route are not used in estimating t_{ETA} . When the residual delay $|t_{ETA} - t_{CTA}|$ exceeds a specified tolerance, the Mach number that minimizes $|t_{ETA} - t_{CTA}|$ is determined. In this study, tolerances of 10 and 30 s are applied. t_{CTA} is set to the same value for both the MDP-based and deterministic speed control approaches, one min later than the initial ETA estimated using the initial speed.

For both the proposed speed control using MDP and the deterministic speed control, a maximum allowable number of speed changes is specified. It is assumed that these changes occur within the preset limit and that the speed cannot be adjusted more frequently than the threshold.

B. Results and Discussion

We compare the proposed speed control using MDP with the deterministic speed control strategy under 10- and 30-s tolerances. Fig. 5 presents the density distributions of delay at the metering fix for 1,205 flights, categorized by the maximum allowable number of speed changes. Tables I and II summarize key statistics, including the mean, standard deviation, and percentile values of delay. The spread of the delay distribution decreases as the maximum allowable number of speed changes increases. For the proposed MDP strategy, the distribution remains unchanged when the maximum allowable number of speed changes reaches 9 or more. In contrast, for the deterministic strategy, the distribution stabilizes at more than 6 speed changes with a 10-s tolerance, and at more than 2 with a 30-s tolerance.

As shown in Fig. 5 and Tables I and II, the proposed MDP strategy reduces the spread of the delay distribution even with a small number of speed changes, such as one

Figure 5: Delay distributions at metering fix.

or two. For instance, when the maximum allowable number of speed changes is two, the deterministic strategy with a 10-s tolerance produces a 90% delay spread (between the 5th and 95th percentiles) of approximately 30 s, ranging from -19 to 11 s. In contrast, the proposed MDP method achieves a narrower 90% spread of about 10 s, ranging from -9 to 1 s, while keeping delays small. Additionally, the MDP strategy maintains a relatively small delay spread of -14 to 3 s for 99% of flights (between the 0.5th and 99.5th percentiles). Furthermore, the proposed MDP method achieves delays of 10 s or less for all flights with three or more speed changes. These results demonstrate that the proposed strategy can achieve smaller delays with fewer speed changes.

Speed changes are performed within the maximum allowable number of changes. These limits are preset. Fig. 6 illustrates the number of speed changes executed for various maximum allowable limits, presented as a stacked bar graph showing the frequency of speed changes across 1,205 flights. Using the proposed MDP method, most flights perform speed changes up to the specified maximum allowable number of changes, particularly when the limit is set to one, two, or three. When the maximum allowable number of speed changes is set to four or more, about 50% of the flights make only two or three speed changes. Conversely, with the deterministic method, approximately 40% of flights make only one speed change, even when the maximum allowable number is two or more. Compared to the deterministic method, the proposed MDP method results in a higher proportion of flights with more speed changes. However, as shown in Fig. 5, it achieves smaller delays overall.

Figs. 7, 8, and 9 illustrate the timing distribution of speed changes. In the deterministic method, the first speed change is always implemented at the initial time step. Since t_{CTA} is set to one min later than the initial ETA estimated using the initial speed, the residual delay, $|t_{ETA} - t_{CTA}|$, always exceeds the tolerance at the initial time step. Consequently, when only one speed change is allowed, no further adjustments can be made after the initial time, leaving the flight susceptible to uncertainties up to the metering fix. In contrast, the proposed MDP method distributes the timing of speed changes, demon-

TABLE I. Delay statistics for speed control strategy using MDP (unit: s).

Statistics	Maximum allowable number of speed changes								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Mean	-4.20	-3.29	-2.09	-1.82	-1.78	-1.77	-1.76	-1.77	-1.76
Standard deviation	4.01	2.82	1.24	0.91	0.84	0.83	0.81	0.82	0.81
99.5%	7.33	2.72	0.36	-0.08	-0.14	-0.16	-0.16	-0.16	-0.16
95%	1.10	0.29	-0.55	-0.64	-0.61	-0.64	-0.63	-0.63	-0.63
Percentile 50%	-4.07	-2.81	-1.90	-1.69	-1.67	-1.66	-1.66	-1.66	-1.66
5%	-9.79	-8.40	-4.17	-3.29	-3.27	-3.26	-3.23	-3.24	-3.23
0.5%	-14.26	-13.36	-7.10	-4.80	-4.10	-4.17	-4.05	-4.10	-4.05

TABLE II. Delay statistics for deterministic speed control strategy with 10- and 30-s tolerances (unit: s).

Statistics	Maximum allowable number of speed changes							
	10-s tolerance						30-s tolerance	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	1	2
Mean	-3.56	-2.48	-1.83	-1.57	-1.64	-1.62	-3.56	-3.64
Standard deviation	15.19	8.61	5.55	4.87	4.78	4.78	15.19	12.34
99.5%	48.39	27.24	15.27	9.93	9.73	9.73	48.39	27.25
95%	23.62	10.28	7.72	7.53	7.39	7.39	23.62	18.79
Percentile 50%	-4.83	-2.46	-2.17	-2.07	-2.09	-2.08	-4.83	-4.72
5%	-28.22	-18.91	-9.52	-8.67	-8.69	-8.67	-28.22	-23.79
0.5%	-37.53	-26.22	-16.86	-9.81	-9.87	-9.81	-37.53	-29.30

Figure 6: Frequency of speed changes for different preset maximum allowable limits.

Figure 7: Timing distributions of speed changes (maximum allowable number of speed changes: one).

strating its ability to implement speed control at optimal times for each flight. Although the residual delay at the initial time step is the same as in the deterministic method, the first speed change in the MDP method is not always implemented at the initial time step, but is instead distributed across later steps. As a result, even when the maximum allowable number of speed changes is limited to one, the MDP method achieves

Figure 8: Timing distributions of speed changes (maximum allowable number of speed changes: two).

Figure 9: Timing distributions of speed changes (maximum allowable number of speed changes: three).

Figure 10: Distributions of changes in speed.

Figure 11: Fuel savings distributions.

smaller delays compared to the deterministic approach. When the maximum allowable number of speed changes is two or three, the deterministic method applies speed changes in an ad hoc manner. By contrast, the MDP method performs the first speed change near the initial time step and the final one closer to the terminal time step. This MDP strategy minimizes delays and ensures speed changes are implemented at appropriate times for each flight, i.e., early adjustments enable better adaptation downstream, while later changes fine-tune the aircraft trajectory as more accurate information with reduced uncertainty becomes available.

Fig. 10 shows the density distributions of the changes in speed.

TABLE III. Fuel savings statistics for speed control strategy using MDP (unit: %).

Statistics	Maximum allowable number of speed changes								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Mean	0.44	2.01	2.28	2.32	2.33	2.33	2.33	2.33	2.33
Standard deviation	0.96	1.39	1.34	1.35	1.35	1.35	1.35	1.35	1.35
99.5%	3.34	5.70	5.94	6.29	6.39	6.31	6.31	6.31	6.31
95%	1.91	4.30	4.72	4.76	4.80	4.80	4.80	4.80	4.80
Percentile 50%	0.37	1.91	2.09	2.14	2.14	2.14	2.14	2.14	2.14
5%	-0.81	-0.14	0.44	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.46	0.46	0.46
0.5%	-2.25	-1.56	-0.26	-0.14	-0.14	-0.14	-0.14	-0.14	-0.14

TABLE IV. Fuel savings statistics for deterministic speed control strategy with 10-s tolerance (unit: %).

Statistics	Maximum allowable number of speed changes				
	2	3	4	5	6
Mean	0.08	0.14	0.17	0.17	0.17
Standard deviation	0.81	0.86	0.86	0.87	0.87
99.5%	2.22	2.80	2.92	2.92	2.92
95%	1.33	1.73	1.76	1.76	1.76
Percentile 50%	0	0	0	0	0
5%	-1.25	-1.25	-1.14	-1.16	-1.16
0.5%	-3.16	-2.43	-2.43	-2.53	-2.53

in speed (Mach number) when the maximum allowable number of speed changes is up to three. Negative speed changes indicate deceleration. Compared to the deterministic approaches, the MDP results in greater deceleration at the final allowable speed change—that is, at the first speed change if the maximum allowable number is one, at the second if the maximum is two, and at the third if the maximum is three. This is because delaying speed changes helps mitigate the impact of uncertainty, and thus a later speed change to accurately meet the CTA requires greater deceleration. Additionally, if the CTA and total flight time remain the same, flying at a slower speed is more cost-effective due to reduced fuel consumption from lower drag and reduced thrust requirements. Therefore, it is believed that the MDP approach incorporates speed changes in a way that further reduces operational costs.

Fuel savings are then evaluated based on fuel consumption determined using the deterministic method with a 30-s tolerance for each maximum allowable number of speed changes. The evaluation focuses exclusively on the analyzed flight distance of 201.5 NM. Fig. 11 illustrates the density distribution of fuel savings for the 1,205 flights analyzed, categorized by the maximum allowable number of speed changes. Additionally, Tables III and IV provide a summary of statistics such as the mean, standard deviation, and percentile values of fuel savings. Using the deterministic method with a 10-s tolerance, the average fuel savings range from 0.1% to 0.2%, which is relatively small. Conversely, with the proposed MDP method, the average fuel savings increase to 0.4% when the maximum allowable number of speed changes is one. Furthermore, when the maximum allowable number of speed changes is two or more, the average fuel savings exceed 2%, highlighting the significantly higher effectiveness of the MDP method. The results also demonstrate that the MDP method achieves positive fuel savings in a large number of flights.

Using the MDP method, speed control is implemented by considering both the cost of delay and the cost of fuel

consumption. Consequently, the numerical simulations in this study demonstrate that small delays can be achieved alongside fuel savings. Even with one or two speed changes, the MDP method outperforms deterministic methods in terms of both delay reduction and fuel savings. In summary, the effectiveness of the proposed MDP method has been successfully demonstrated through the numerical simulations.

Finally, it should be noted that the numerical simulation evaluations in this study did not account for potential conflicts between aircraft, as they were conducted for individual flights. In actual operations, ensuring aircraft separation is crucial before changing speeds for time-based metering. Therefore, future research should address potential conflicts when implementing speed control for time-based metering in real-world operations. Additionally, though this study allowed for speed changes at consecutive time steps, frequent speed changes over a short period may not be acceptable to pilots or air traffic controllers. Such operational constraints need to be taken into account. Furthermore, while this study focused on cruise speed control along the planned route, there are inherent limitations to the extent flight time can be adjusted solely through this strategy. For longer flight time adjustments, flight-level changes or path stretching via radar vectoring may be necessary. Hence, future research should explore not only speed control but also flight-level changes and path stretching to enable more flexible flight time adjustments.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study proposed a stochastic speed control framework using an MDP to improve time-based metering under uncertainty, balancing delay uncertainty with operational costs from speed changes. Numerical simulations showed the method effectively reduced delay variability and improved adherence to CTAs, even with limited speed changes. Unlike deterministic approaches, the MDP method optimized the timing of speed adjustments, enhancing flexibility and reducing susceptibility to uncertainties. The framework achieved over 2% average fuel savings with a limited number of speed changes,

demonstrating both delay reduction and fuel efficiency. This highlights its potential for practical implementation, as fewer speed changes reduce the workload for pilots and air traffic controllers and simplify operations.

Although validated for individual flights, future research should address separation assurance and explore complementary strategies, such as flight-level changes or path stretching, to better reflect real-world operations and enable greater flexibility. Overall, the proposed MDP-based method advances trajectory uncertainty management, offering a robust and practical approach to safer and more efficient air traffic operations.

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